

AIR QUALITY IN BOR DURING THE TRIAL OPERATION OF THE COPPER SMELTER AFTER THE RECONSTRUCTION

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of the air quality measurements conducted at the Jugopetrol (JP), Brezonik (BR), Krivelj (KR), and Oštrelj (OS) sites, as a part of the air quality monitoring program within the territory of Bor, covering the period from August 2023 to July 2024. At the JP, BR, and OS monitoring sites, the number of days exceeding the daily limit value surpassed 35 days. At the JP site, exceedances of the daily limit value for lead concentration in PM₁₀ were recorded on eight occasions. Additionally, at the JP site, the average concentrations of cadmium and arsenic in PM₁₀ exceeded the annual target values. Similarly, at the BR site, the average concentration of arsenic in PM₁₀ was found to be higher than the annual target value. During the trial operation period of the copper smelter, the JP site recorded 33 days where arsenic concentrations in PM₁₀ were more than 20 times higher than the target annual value (6 ng/m³). Furthermore, at the same site, cadmium concentrations in PM₁₀ exceeded the target annual value (5 ng/m³) by more than 20 times on three days. These findings suggest that, despite the recent reconstruction efforts, the issue of elevated emissions of carcinogenic elements in PM₁₀ from the Copper Smelter persists. Therefore, the urgent implementation of additional measures is necessary to reduce these emissions to comply with legally prescribed limits.

Keywords: Copper Smelter, air pollution, suspended particles, arsenic, cadmium

1. INTRODUCTION

Copper ore has been extracted and processed within the city of Bor, Serbia, for over a century. The activities associated with copper ore mining and processing have resulted in numerous adverse environmental impacts, affecting the air, water, and soil quality, and have raised significant concerns regarding their implications for the human health [1,2,3]. Since 2005, the automated methods for measuring the sulfur dioxide (SO₂) concentrations have been implemented at various monitoring stations across the city [4,5,6]. Due to the construction of the high mining dumps, there was a change in the direction of winds and increase in the period without wind (silence). This led to a PM₁₀ level increase in Bor because the natural ventilation was reduced [7,8]. The air pollution in the urban environment of the city of Bor occurs during mining operations and various metallurgical activities in the Copper Smelter in Bor [9]. In the last few years, an important factor that affected the air quality in Bor was the change of ownership of the Copper Smelter at the end of 2018. One of the world's leading companies in copper and

precious metals production, Zijin [10] became a strategic partner with the majority ownership in the Copper Smelter Bor. In 2023, the expansion of the Copper Smelter capacity, as well as the construction of a new Sulfuric Acid Plant, a new Electrolysis Facility, and additional supporting infrastructure, were completed [11]. To further highlight the issue of air pollution in Bor, this study analyzes the air quality in the city from August 2023 to July 2024.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Daily samples of PM₁₀ were collected at the measuring sites Jugopetrol (JP), Brezonik (BR), Krivelj (KR), and Oštrej (OS) (shown in Figure 1) with the LIFETEK PMS and SL MVS6 samplers, operating at an airflow rate of 55 m³/24 h, with the PM₁₀ sampling heads, in the period August 2023 - July 2024. Quartz filters of the Frisenette Grade QF 47 mm variant were utilized for the PM₁₀ sampling. The filters were weighed following the procedure outlined in the standard SRPS EN12341:2015 [12]. For chemical analysis preparation, the methodology outlined in SRPS EN 14902:2008 [13] was strictly followed. Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) using an Agilent model 7700 was employed to determine the concentrations of lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), and arsenic (As) in PM₁₀ samples. To ensure the quality control and validate the dissolution and analysis procedure, the standard reference material NIST 1648a [14] was analyzed using the same protocols as the PM₁₀ samples, with the recovery rates for all analyzed elements ranging between 85% and 115%. The prevailing wind direction in Bor, is the west-northwest, as shown in Figure 1. Meteorological conditions with no wind (silence - wind speed is less than 1 m/s) occur regularly (more than 50% of the day).

Figure 1. Position of the sites KR, BR, OS, and JP relative to the Copper Smelter Bor

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the average values of PM₁₀ and Pb, Cd, Ni, and As levels at the JP, BR, KR, and OS sites in the whole period of measurements. The results presented in Table 1 show that in the observed period, no exceedances of the annual limit value for the PM₁₀ concentrations were recorded at any measuring point.

Table 1. Average values of the PM_{10} , Pb, Cd, Ni, and As levels (exceeding the daily limit - EDL, exceeding annual target value *10 - ETV10) in the period August 2023-July 2024

	PM_{10}	EDL PM_{10}	Pb	EDL Pb	Cd	ETV10 Cd	Ni	As	ETV10 As
	$\mu g/m^3$	days	$\mu g/m^3$	days	ng/m^3	days	ng/m^3	ng/m^3	days
JP	33.6	45	0.21	8	17.2	23	2.6	46.4	83
BR	36.8	57	0.03	0	3.9	0	2.1	8.8	1
KR	27.2	13	0.01	0	1.1	0	2.3	2.3	0
OS	29.9	35	0.01	0	1.7	0	2.3	4.1	0

However, the exceedances of the limit value for the average daily concentration of PM_{10} were recorded at the sites: JP (45 days), BR (57 days), KR (13 days), and OS (35 days). In the observed period, the exceedances of the limit value for the average daily concentration of Pb in PM_{10} were recorded at the JP site (8 days). In the observed period, the annual target value for the concentration of Cd in PM_{10} was exceeded at the JP site. In the observed period, the Cd concentrations in PM_{10} over 10 times higher than the target annual value ($5 ng/m^3$) were recorded in 23 days at the JP site. In the observed period, the annual target value for Ni concentration in PM_{10} was not exceeded at any site. In the observed period, the annual target value for the concentration of As in PM_{10} was exceeded at the sites JP and BR. In the observed period, the As concentrations in PM_{10} over 10 times higher than the annual target value ($6 ng/m^3$) were recorded in 83 days at the JP site, and in one day at the BR site.

Figure 2. Average daily concentrations of Cd in PM_{10} in the period August 2023-July 2024

Figure 3. Average daily concentrations of As in PM₁₀ in the period August 2023-July 2024

Figures 2 and 3 clearly illustrate the elevated concentrations of As and Cd levels in PM₁₀ at the JP monitoring site compared to the levels of these elements in PM₁₀ at the other observed locations. During the reconstruction period of the Copper Smelter (May 2022 - April 2023), the concentrations of As and Cd in PM₁₀ at the JP monitoring site were not as elevated as those observed during the trial operation period of the Smelter [15]. Considering that the JP site is located in the predominant wind direction that transports air pollution from the Copper Smelter, the high concentrations of As and Cd detected at this site can be attributed to the emissions from the Smelter, specifically resulting from the processing of copper concentrate with the elevated levels of As and Cd. This indicates that the concentration of these carcinogenic elements in the copper concentrate exceeded the levels anticipated in the environmental impact assessment for the project, "Increasing the Capacity of the Copper Smelter within the Serbia Zijin Copper DOO Complex" [11], during certain periods.

4. CONCLUSION

Despite the reconstruction of the Copper Smelter, the problem of emission of high concentrations of carcinogenic elements in PM₁₀ from the Copper Smelter is still present in Bor. Due to this reason, it is necessary to urgently apply the additional measures to reduce these emissions to the values provided by the law. Consequently, it is imperative to implement the additional measures for regular monitoring the composition of concentrates processed at the Bor Copper Smelter, ensuring alignment with the prescribed values, outlined in the environmental impact assessment study [11]. This will be necessary to reduce the content of carcinogenic elements in the PM₁₀ fraction of suspended particles to the levels that comply with the legal standards.

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